

The Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) and its Implementation in Brunei Darussalam's Juvenile Justice System

Yusuf Ibrahim Arowosaiye

*Sultan Haji Hassanal Bolkiyah Faculty of Law,
Sultan Sharif Ali Islamic University, Brunei Darussalam*

Ahmad Masum

*Sultan Haji Hassanal Bolkiyah Faculty of Law,
Sultan Sharif Ali Islamic University, Brunei Darussalam*

Hajah Hanan Hj Awang Abdul Aziz

*Sultan Haji Hassanal Bolkiyah Faculty of Law,
Sultan Sharif Ali Islamic University, Brunei Darussalam*

Rajali Haji Aji

*Sultan Haji Hassanal Bolkiyah Faculty of Law,
Sultan Sharif Ali Islamic University, Brunei Darussalam*

Siti Nur Umaimah Haji Lukman

*PhD Candidate, Sultan Haji Hassanal Bolkiyah Faculty of Law,
Sultan Sharif Ali Islamic University, Brunei Darussalam*

Abstract

The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) is an international convention and an agreement among countries to protect children's rights. The ratification of the CRC implies commitment to uphold its principles and to be accountable to the international community based on the CRC's obligations. Brunei Darussalam has been a signatory to the CRC since 1995 and has undertaken legal and institutional reforms to align its juvenile justice system with the international child rights standards. This paper examines the extent to which Brunei Darussalam's juvenile justice system, policies, and practices align with the four core principles of the CRC: the best interests of the child, non-discrimination, participation, and the right to protection from inhumane treatment. The paper analyses Brunei Darussalam's statutory provisions on juvenile justice, such as the Children and Young Persons Act (CYPA) and recent amendments to juvenile procedures and assesses their practical application in judicial and correctional settings. Using the legal analysis method and case studies/policy reviews, the paper identifies progress made in the promotion of child rights and fulfilment of Brunei's international obligations under the CRC. Challenges in translating CRC obligations into practice were identified. The paper highlights the gaps in implementation caused by limited institutional capacity, lack of awareness, and inconsistencies in enforcement. The paper concludes by advocating for juvenile justice policy reform, capacity building among juvenile justice actors, and strengthening of Brunei Darussalam's juvenile justice system to fully align with CRC standards.

Keywords: *Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), juvenile justice, child rights, Children and Young Persons Act (CYPA), juvenile offenders.*

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Introduction

In 1989, the General Assembly of the United Nations adopted the Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC), marking a turning point in the global quest for a legal regime to recognise and protect the rights of the child. The CRC entered into force in 1990 following its unprecedented ratification by most member states. The CRC has been acclaimed as the most ratified human rights treaty in the history of the United Nations. Almost all nations of the world ratified the Convention except the United States, despite the US's active participation in the drafting of the Convention. The Convention provides the principal framework for child rights in the administration of the juvenile justice system by requiring that children in conflict with the law or accused of criminal acts be treated with observance of their dignity, and it promotes reintegration and community engagements in the juvenile justice system as opposed to punishment (United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, 1989).

The CRC was ratified by Brunei Darussalam on 27 December 1995, and by this Brunei Darussalam is committed to its obligations under the treaty. Brunei Darussalam, like some other countries of the world who are also signatories to the Convention, registered reservations in relation to some aspects of the Convention, some of which will be highlighted in the later part of this paper under the juvenile justice system (United Nations, 1995). The CRC is a composite convention on the rights of the child; however, our preoccupation in this paper focuses on the juvenile justice system aspect of the convention and its implementation under the Brunei Darussalam juvenile justice system. In this wise, attention will be directed to the relevant provisions of the CRC on the basic framework for the implementation of an efficient and effective juvenile justice system. The CRC provisions guide member states, Brunei Darussalam inclusive, on the key achievable elements that a juvenile justice system should include in accordance with the UN Standard Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice.

State parties to the CRC Convention are under obligation to observe and respect the rights of children alleged as accused of or recognised as having infringed the relevant provisions of the penal code. The CRC requires state parties to treat children in conflict with the law with due observance of the provisions of Articles 37 and 40 of the CRC. They are expected to develop and implement a comprehensive juvenile justice policy and establish an effective administration of juvenile justice that operates in conscious compliance with relevant provisions of the CRC. They are also to take into consideration the general principles enshrined in Articles 2, 3, 6, and 12 and other relevant articles of the CRC, such as Articles 4 and 39. Brunei Darussalam has consistently evolved in its commitment to implement these principles and observe the relevant provisions of the CRC towards achieving full compliance with the CRC. This is so in the areas of procedural rights, the development and implementation of measures for dealing with children in conflict with the law devoid of regular judicial proceedings, and imprisonment as a measure of last resort (Committee on the Rights of the Child, 2007). But the question remains how effective the measures and policies are, if any, that Brunei Darussalam has put in place to prevent children from coming into conflict with the law.

Thus, this paper examines the extent Brunei Darussalam has incorporated and implemented the CRC in its administration of the juvenile justice system. Is the extant Brunei Darussalam juvenile justice system promoting the use of alternative measures such as diversion and restorative justice, which engenders an effective response to children in conflict with the law in a way that serves the best interests of the children and the short- and long-term interests of the society at large? It is instructive to note that juvenile justice in Brunei Darussalam is governed by corpus domestic laws and administered by institutions. A few of these domestic laws include the Children and Young Persons Act (Cap. 219), the Penal Code (Cap. 22), the Syariah Penal Code (Cap. 275), and Juvenile Court.

Overview Of the CRC Core Principles and Provisions on Juvenile Justice

It is instructive to note that the scope of the CRC covers a wider spectrum of issues relating to the general rights of children, which includes civil, economic, political, and cultural rights for children. However, CRC's provisions on juvenile justice have been adjudged as the most comprehensive and innovative attempt at setting the global minimum standards for the juvenile justice system and administration. State parties are required to harmonise their national juvenile justice system, policies, and legislation along the CRC's core principles for treating children who conflict with penal provisions. These principles, as will be shortly discussed here, emphasized the need to uphold human rights, dignity, fairness, and the promotion of rehabilitation and reintegration into society of children in conflict with the law. It also restricts the use of detention to a measure of last resort (United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, 1989).

Here we shall examine the core four CRC principles guiding the implementation of all rights under the CRC, with specific focus on the provisions relating to juvenile justice (United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child 1989). The provisions on juvenile justice will be analyzed, and its implications for states parties' juvenile justice practices.

Non-Discrimination (Article 2)

Article 2 of the CRC prohibits any forms of discrimination against children in conflict with the law, and they are treated equally regardless of their race, language, religion, sex, disability, nationality or ethnic origin, or any other status. It has been observed that discrimination and disparities resulting from inconsistent juvenile justice policy reflect on the vulnerability of some children. These classes of children include street children, children belonging to racial, ethnic, religious, or linguistic minorities, indigenous children, girl children, children with disabilities, and children who are repeatedly in conflict with the law (recidivists) (Committee on the Rights of the Child, 2007).

In this regard, Article 2 of the CRC to guarantee equal access to legal protections and fair trial rights, prevent discriminatory policing, prosecution, or sentencing practices, and address systemic inequalities faced by minority and marginalised children. The United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child is seriously concerned about the disproportionate representation of minority children in justice systems worldwide, urging states to address structural discrimination (Committee on the Rights of the Child, 2014).

Best Interests of the Child (Article 3)

The best interests of the child should be the main consideration in making policy and taking decisions in relation to juvenile justice administration. The physical and psychological development and emotional state of mind of children are quite different from that of adults. These apparent differences should be taken into consideration in determining criminal culpability of children who are in conflict with the law. In other words, these factors constitute the basis for lesser culpability of children in conflict with the law and the reason why children in conflict with the law should be treated differently from adult offenders.

Article 3 of the CRC regarding the "best interests of the child" demands that juvenile justice practices in relation to issues of arrest, detention, trial, or sentencing must put into consideration the ultimate best interests of children in conflict with the law by prioritising their welfare, emotional and psychological concerns, development, and long-term reintegration. The protection of the best interests of the child entails that the ordinary objectives of criminal justice, such as retribution and punishment in the nature of imprisonment and deprivation of freedom, which are suitable for adult offenders, should not be applicable to children. Rather, the juvenile justice objectives should promote restorative justice and rehabilitation of children in conflict with the law.

Right to Life, Survival, and Development (Article 6)

Article 6 of the CRC affirms that children have the right to live a full life, while state parties should ensure that children survive and develop healthily. It is the responsibility of governments to develop effective juvenile justice policies and programmes for the prevention of juvenile delinquency and its negative

impacts on the child's development. To fully realize the inherent rights to life under the Article of CRC, capital punishment, death sentences, and life imprisonment without parole are explicitly prohibited under Article 37 (a) of CRC. Keeping children in conflict with the law in prison, especially with adult prisoners or in the same facilities, will have negative consequences for the child's physical, mental, spiritual, moral, and social development and make their reintegration back into society more difficult.

According to Article 37 (b) of the CRC, the deprivation of liberty in the juvenile justice system should be used only as a measure of last resort and for the shortest appropriate period. This is to preserve the child's right to development and survival. It is instructive to note that in certain circumstances, the rights of a child deprived of his/her liberty due to his/her conflict with the law, as recognized in the CRC, apply with respect to children in conflict with the law and to children placed in institutions for the purposes of care, protection, or treatment, including mental health, educational, drug treatment, child protection, or immigration institutions (Committee on the Rights of the Child, 2014).

The Right to be Heard (Article 12)

Article 12 of the CRC guarantees children the right to say what they think should happen when adults are making decisions that affect them and to have their opinions considered. The maturity and age of children in question will often be considered in respect of the views of the child. State parties are expected to respect the right of children to express their views freely in all matters relating to juvenile justice and implement the same at every stage of the process of juvenile justice. The United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child observes that the voices of children involved in the juvenile justice system and their perspectives are playing an increasingly influential role in driving reforms, advancing improvements, and ensuring the realization of their rights (Committee on the Rights of the Child, 2014).

The right of the child to be heard may manifest in the juvenile justice system by direct opportunity to effectively participate in proceedings or through representatives. The right to be heard includes the right of access to child-friendly legal information and their meaningful participation in restorative justice processes. It is expected that state parties will accord their views resinous consideration and respect these views in decision-making, especially on matters as serious as that of diversion programmes and restorative justice goals and align with the CRC's core principles of juvenile justice (Committee on the Rights of the Child, 2009).

CRC Principal Provisions on Juvenile Justice

The above core principles of CRC provide an essential framework for the global juvenile justice system, and they apply broadly. There are, however, specific provisions under CRC dedicated to the juvenile justice system. Articles 37 and 40 of the CRC contain the specific provisions on the juvenile justice system and are complemented by other relevant articles and further supplemented by international legal instruments such as the United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice (Beijing Rules, 1985), the United Nations Guidelines for the Prevention of Juvenile Delinquency (Riyadh Guidelines, 1990), and the United Nations Rules for the Protection of Juveniles Deprived of their Liberty (Havana Rules, 1990).

Deprivation of Liberty (Article 37)

The treatment of children in conflict with the law under any criminal justice system represents a delicate intersection of law, ethics, and psychology, especially in the observance of the international legal framework for the right of the child. Article 37 of the CRC contains the basic principles of protecting the rights and dignity of children in conflict with the law. Article 37 affirms the fundamental requirements in the juvenile justice system to treat children with dignity and respect and highlights specific protections against torture, degradation of treatment or punishment and arbitrary deprivation of liberty during juvenile justice administration. Article 37 emphasizes that the detention must be a measure of last resort and for the shortest period of appropriate time. States parties are to adhere to the basic principles stipulated under Article 37 of the Convention and many other relevant provisions.

Article 37 expressed the need for the juvenile justice system to promote the philosophy of rehabilitation and reintegration as opposed to punitive measures in relation to child offenders. According to Manco, the traditional view that is equivalent to dissuasive punishment is fundamentally in disagreement with the intention of central rehabilitation for youth justice systems (Manco, 2015). The recognition of children as holders of rights, instead of mere criminals, places a significant emphasis on their unique development needs and rehabilitation potential.

Article 37 sets out limitations on the use of deprivation of liberty or imprisonment for children, which shall be in conformity with the law and to be used only as a means of last resort and for the shortest appropriate period. And that no child shall be deprived of his or her liberty unlawfully or arbitrarily, and no torture or cruel, inhuman, or degrading treatment be directed at children in conflict with the law. This is a reinforcement of the international standards against torture (Convention against Torture and other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment 1984). Article 37 prohibits capital punishment and life imprisonment without the opportunity of parole. Procedurally, every child arrested and deprived of his or her liberty has the right to prompt access to legal and other appropriate assistance and can challenge the legality of the deprivation of his or her liberty (Convention on the Rights of the Child 1989). Article 37(d) prohibits the placing of children in conflict with the law in prison facilities for adults, as this will compromise their safety, well-being, and the subsequent rehabilitation and reintegration processes (Convention on the Rights of the Child 1989). Article 37 thus provides a strong human rights framework against excessive criminalisation and institutionalization of children. It also codifies the human rights principles and practices to be applicable to juvenile justice systems worldwide. By this, Article 37 emphasises the unique nature of juvenile justice by recognising the fact that children are amenable to rehabilitation and therefore should not be subjected to harsh conditions as punishment and imprisonment like adults.

Administration of Juvenile Justice (Article 40)

To give effect to the basic principles of juvenile justice as enunciated under Article 37 of the CRC, it is imperative for state parties to put in place an effective organization or institutions for the implementation of juvenile justice and administration. According to Article 40 (3) of the CRC, state parties shall seek to promote the establishment of laws, procedures, authorities, and institutions specifically applicable to children in conflict with the penal law. For this reason, Article 40 provides that child alleged, accused, or recognised as having conflict with the relevant penal law are entitled to guarantees that reflect their age and aim at reintegration.

Dignity and Worth

Article 40 of the CRC provides a set of basic principles for the treatment of children in conflict with the law. A few of these fundamental principles will be discussed here. Article 40 (1) provides that treatment of children in conflict with the law should be consistent with the child's sense of dignity and worth (United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, 1989). This is affirming the fundamental human right provision of Article 1 of the UDHR, which provides that all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. The child's inherent right to dignity and worth is to be respected by state parties and safeguarded at every stage and process of the juvenile justice system.

Minimum Age of Criminal Responsibility

Article 40 of the CRC does not specifically set the minimum age of criminal responsibility (MACR); however, it requires State Parties to establish what it considers an appropriate age below which children shall not be presumed to possess the required capacity to commit crime and be culpable. Article 40 (3) (a) CRC provides:

“States Parties shall seek to promote the establishment of laws, procedures, authorities and institutions specifically applicable to children alleged as, accused of, or recognised as having infringed the penal law, and, in particular: (a) The establishment of a minimum age below which children shall be presumed not to have the capacity to infringe the penal law.”

Due to the flexibility of the above minimum requirement for the setting of MACR, it was observed that State Parties have a wide range of minimum ages of criminal responsibility, which range from a low level of age of 7 or 8 to the commendable high level of age of 14 or 16 (Committee on the Rights of the Child, 2007). It is, however, instructive to note that the United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child, in its General Comment No. 10 (2007), recommends that the minimum age should not be lower than 12 years but encourages State Parties to raise it to 14 or 16 years to ensure a stronger protection for the rights of the child.

Minimum Guarantees of a Fair Trial

A fair trial is a cardinal principle of justice, especially in criminal proceedings. This long-standing principle is also enshrined in Article 40 (2) of the CRC, which contains a list of rights that are to guarantee a fair trial for children in conflict with the law in juvenile justice proceedings (International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights 1966). Thus, children accused of breaking the law are entitled to the following rights for a fair trial: presumed innocent until proven guilty; informed promptly and directly of the charges, with legal or other assistance; matter to be determined without delay, before an impartial authority, with assistance, and with involvement of parents or guardians where appropriate; not compelled to give testimony or confess guilt, i.e. freedom from compulsory self-incrimination, right to examine witnesses and to obtain witnesses under equal conditions; fair assistance of an interpreter if child cannot understand the language, no retroactive juvenile justice and the privacy of the child to be fully respected at all stages of the proceedings (United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, 1989).

Diversion and Alternatives

Here States Parties are encouraged to explore two forms of interventions for dealing with children alleged as, accused of, or recognized as having infringed the penal law. These include measures without resorting to judicial proceedings and measures in the framework of juvenile justice proceedings. States are to promote and ensure that the child's human rights are respected and the necessary legal safeguards in juvenile justice proceedings are observed. Examples of these forms of interventions include counselling, probation, mediation, guidance, and supervision; foster care; and other community-based programs such as educational and training programmes and other alternatives to institutional care (United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, 1989).

As part of intervention without resorting to judicial proceedings, Article 40 (3) of the CRC provides that the State parties shall seek to promote measures for dealing with children alleged as, accused of, or recognised as having infringed the penal law without resorting to judicial proceedings, whenever appropriate and desirable. This provision is important to address situations where the offence committed by a child offender is a minor offence. Removing such commission of crime from juvenile justice proceedings and referral to alternative social service (i.e., diversion) will serve the end of justice better, which is not to punish but to rehabilitate the child offender from further commission of serious offences and avoid stigmatization. States Parties are encouraged to consider this as the best practice to be used in such a situation.

Other UN Standards Complementing the CRC

The provisions of CRC in relation to the rights of a child in juvenile justice are complemented by several other United Nations legal instruments on standards and guidelines on the same subject matter of juvenile justice. Although State Parties are provided with practical guidance to be adopted in fashioning their juvenile justice system and administration, these UN legal instruments are mere treaties without any legally binding effect. However, they are useful as authoritative tools for interpretations of international juvenile justice standards and a viable tool in evaluating State Parties' compliance with the relevant CRC's fundamental principle and provisions on juvenile justice. The other UN standards complementing legal instruments which reinforced the CRC's provisions are the following.

The Beijing Rules (1985)

The United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice (Beijing Rules, 1985), being the first international legal instrument to address juvenile justice, highlight the well-being of juveniles as the guiding principle in the juvenile justice system. It also emphasises the use of diversionary measures without resorting to formal trial by the competent authority (Beijing Rules 1985). The Beijing Rules laid down detailed guidelines in relation to issues of investigation, arrest, pre-trial detention, trial, sentencing, and post-trial measures. The ideals of proportionality, rehabilitation, and minimum intervention were emphasised in the Beijing Rules, which are features of Articles 37 and 40 of the CRC.

UN Guidelines for the Prevention of Juvenile Delinquency (Riyadh Guidelines, 1990)

The Riyadh guidelines of 1990 emphasis the role of the family, the importance of prevention strategies, education and social inclusion, community engagement, and creating a conducive environment that will prevent delinquency (Riyadh Guidelines 1990).

UN Rules for the Protection of Juveniles Deprived of their Liberty (Havana Rules, 1990)

The Havana Rules (1990) set out minimum standards for the treatment of children in detention (Havana Rules 1990). It is an extension of Article 37 of the CRC by focusing on best practice in juvenile justice in relation to conditions of detention by stipulating the requirement of separating child offenders from adult offenders, access to education and vocational training, access to families, and good healthcare services. All these requirements are part of the humane treatment of a child in conflict with the law under detention. The Havana Rules emphasise that deprivation of liberty should always be an exceptional measure and implemented in conditions that safeguard the dignity and developmental needs of the child.

Implementation and Analysis of the CRC in Brunei Darussalam Juvenile Justice System

As reiterated above, the CRC laid the foundation for comprehensive legal principles and guidelines for the protection of the rights of children. The CRC establishes guidelines and a legal framework which oblige the States Parties to prioritise the rights of children and put in place a juvenile justice system that protects the rights of the children accused of offences to be treated in a manner that promotes dignity, reintegration, and community engagement in rehabilitating children who are in conflict with the law. Brunei Darussalam acceded to the CRC on 27 December 1995 with some reservations (general and specific) to Articles 14, 20, and 21 of the CRC. Although it is the prerogative of State Parties to express reservations to some of the provisions of the CRC, Brunei's reservations will continue to influence the interface between the CRC's standards and Brunei's domestic legislation and institutional framework on the juvenile justice system (United Nations Treaty Collections, n.d.). A good example is the issue of minimum ages of criminal responsibility recommended under CRC, not lower than 12 and preferably higher (Committee on the Rights of the Child, 2007), the promotion of rehabilitation in juvenile justice administration, and the use of non-custodial measures (Committee on the Rights of the Child, 2019).

This section of the paper evaluates the extent to which Brunei Darussalam has incorporated and implemented the CRC in its juvenile justice system, policy, and practice. Here, Brunei Darussalam's treaty status, national legislations and juvenile justice framework are synthesised, and recommendations are provided as the concluding part of this paper.

Brunei Darussalam CRC Treaty Status, International Guidance and Reservations

On 27 December 1995, Brunei Darussalam acceded to the CRC, with the instrument of accession indicating broad general and specific reservations to any provisions of the CRC that are contrary to the Constitution and to the religion of Islam and its principles. Of the provisions of the CRC for which reservations were expressed are Articles 14, which borders on freedom of thought, conscience, and religion, 20 (alternative care), and 21 (adoption). It is instructive to note that the reservations in respect

of Articles 20 and 21 were later withdrawn (Status of the Convention on the Rights of the Child – Brunei Darussalam 1995) (Human Rights Watch, n.d.).

Brunei Darussalam again acceded to the Optional Protocol on the Sale of Children, Child Prostitution and Child Pornography (OPSC) on 21 November 2006 (National University of Singapore, 2000). Ten years later, it acceded to the Optional Protocol on the Involvement of Children in Armed Conflict (OPAC) on 17 May 2016 (Office of the High Commissioner, n.d.).

Brunei Darussalam’s Domestic Legal and Institutional Framework for the Juvenile Justice System

Brunei Darussalam’s legal system is steeped in plurality, with the dual status of civil and Syariah law operating side by side within their defined legal and courts’ jurisdictional ambit. The two legal norms under the same Brunei Darussalam legal system contain related basic legal instruments concerning juvenile justice and administration.

Children and Young Persons Act (CYPA) (Cap. 219)

Sequel to the enactment of the Children and Young Persons Act in 2006, the youth justice system in Brunei Darussalam was characterised by punitive measures that are antithetical to the needs and rights of development of children. The juvenile justice system then embraced a retributive philosophical tendency to punish child offenders in the same manner as adult offenders without any transformative approach to address youth delinquency.

The CYPA, implemented on 1st March 2010, replaced the Children and Young Persons Order in 2006 (Judiciary of Brunei Darussalam, n.d.). This piece of legislation marked the watershed in the development of Brunei’s juvenile justice system, addressing various aspects of a child’s rights, including prevention, inspection and rehabilitation measures, protection orders, and welfare and care of the child that are necessary for an effective and right-guarded juvenile justice system. The legislation aims to reform Brunei Darussalam’s child justice system and is a critical legal development towards compliance with the core principles of the CRC and obligations under the Convention. The CYPA incorporates many of the core principles in the CRC by emphasising the need for non-custodial measures as an alternative for imprisonment and the need to safeguard children against all forms of violence and abuse.

Section 2 (1) (a) of the CYPA 2006, which is the interpretation section of the Act, defines “child” as a person under the age of 14 years, “young person” as a person who has attained the age of 14 years but who has not attained the age of 18 years, and “juvenile” as a person who has attained the age of 7 years but who has not attained the age of 18 years. One of the features of CYPA is that it vested in juvenile courts and welfare authorities’ powers to order protective. It also provides for rehabilitative measures and regulates procedures and sentencing limitations for juveniles. These include special procedures and preference for care/rehabilitation. The application of the provisions of CYPA is connected to other related legislations that regulate child justice, such as the Penal Code and Criminal Procedure Code, and with administrative structures coordinated by the Department of Community Development (JAPEM) under the Ministry of Culture, Youth and Sports (MCYS) (Judiciary of Brunei Darussalam, n.d.) (Ministry of Culture, Youth & Sports, n.d.)

Penal Code (Cap. 22) and Criminal Procedure Code (Cap. 7) (revised 2016)

The Penal Code represents the principal legislation that sets out the general provisions on criminal law. It also contains some provisions on infancy and criminal responsibility. Section 82 of the Penal Code incorporates the common law principle of *doli incapax*, granting complete immunity from criminal responsibility to young children. According to section 82 of the Penal Code, nothing is an offence which is done by a child under the age of 7 years. This section sets the minimum age of criminal responsibility in Brunei Darussalam effectively at 7 years, and it represents an irrebuttable presumption of incapacity (*doli incapax*). Section 83 of the Penal Code establishes a rebuttable presumption of incapacity for older children. According to section 83, “Nothing is an offence which is done by a child above the age of 7 years and under the age of 12 years, who has not attained sufficient maturity of understanding to judge

the nature and consequences of his conduct on that occasion.” This is actually a rebuttable presumption of incapacity, and it has to be established that the alleged criminal act of a child above 7 and under 12 was done with an immature understanding of whether the act was wrong or right by the child. The combined provisions of sections 82 and 83 of the Penal Code established a low Minimum Age of Criminal Responsibility (MACR) in Brunei Darussalam juvenile justice practice (Penal Code 1951) (Child Rights International Network, 2010)

The procedural aspect of criminal justice is governed by the Criminal Procedure Code (Cap. 7), and it is also applicable to the operations of the CYPA and specialised court rules (Criminal Procedure Code 1951) (Penal Code 1951). The CPC (revised 2016) provides for the procedure relating to the trial of youthful offenders and the special court powers and sentencing and canning procedures and sets the limit in respect of juveniles.

Syariah Penal Code (Cap. 275)

The Syariah Penal Code (Cap. 275) represents the Islamic law criminal code that is applicable to Muslim offenders in respect of certain offences and provides for penalties. It has a distinct concept of infancy which determines the Minimum Age of Criminal Responsibility (MACR). Rather than stating the exact minimum age of criminal responsibility, the Syariah Penal Code determines the minimum age of criminal responsibility based on the capacity of a child to distinguish what is right from what is wrong. According to the provision of section 12 of the Syariah Penal Code, nothing is an offence which is done by a child who is not *mumaiyiz*. Thus, an act by a child, for example, who is not *mumaiyiz* is not an offence and has no criminal liability under Syariah evidentiary concepts (Syariah Penal Code 2013) (International Commission of Jurists, 2015). This means non-liability for non-*mukallaf/mumaiyiz* under the Syariah evidentiary rules in Brunei. According to section 3(1) of the Syariah Courts Evidence Order, 2001 (S 63/2001), “*mumaiyiz*” means a child who has attained the age of being capable of differentiating a matter.

However, in the case of a criminal act of a child who is *mumaiyiz* but not *baligh*, such a child will be criminally responsible and punished, except that *hadd or qisas* punishment would not be imposed. Section 13 of the Syariah Penal Code provides, “No *hadd or qisas* punishment may be imposed on any offence liable to *hadd or qisas* punishment committed by a *mumaiyiz* child who is not *baligh* but may be punished with punishments other than *hadd or qisas*.”

The above provisions of sections 12 and 13 of the Syariah Penal Code presented a complex evidential threshold for the determination of MACR. While section 12 provides a complete immunity from criminal responsibility for non-*mukallaf/mumaiyiz*, the provision of section 13 of the Syariah Penal Code still permits the use of corporal punishment and other severe sanctions for a *mumaiyiz* child who is not *baligh*.

These provisions, rules of evidence, and sanctions in respect of juvenile justice proceedings under the Syariah juvenile justice framework call for evaluation as to whether the ideal principle in Article 37 of the CRC is observed and incorporated. For instance, corporal penalties or severe sanctions within the Syariah legal framework are not in tandem with the juvenile justice requirements under the CRC and other international human rights norms (Human Rights Watch, 2019) (Child Rights Network, 2012).

Institutions: Juvenile Court

The ratification of the CRC culminated in substantial juvenile justice reforms in Brunei Darussalam. One of the legal reforms in the Brunei Darussalam youth justice system is the establishment of specialised courts and a change of approach in child justice towards a rehabilitation model. The specialized juvenile court, a subordinate court status, operated within all the districts. It has criminal jurisdiction over offences committed by persons below the age of 18 years who are “beyond parental control” and criminal matters on the issue of care and protection (Judiciary of Brunei Darussalam, n.d.).

Juvenile court adopts measures that promote welfare, guidance, and rehabilitation of child offenders. These measures are pursued by the court in collaboration with Jabatan Pembangunan Masyarakat (JAPEM), i.e., the Department of Community Development (under the Ministry of Culture, Youth and Sports), and other stakeholders (Ministry of Culture, Youth & Sports, n.d.). Juvenile court is presided

over by a magistrate appointed by His Majesty the Sultan of Brunei Darussalam (Judiciary of Brunei Darussalam, n.d.).

Probation and Community-Based Measures

As part of the structural and institutional reform of the juvenile justice system, Brunei Darussalam has put in place probation and community service structures with the Community Development Officer designated as Chief Probation Officer. This is also completed with the establishment of a Probation Committee under subsidiary legislation. JAPEM is responsible for the coordination of child protection initiatives and provides social services that interface with juvenile cases (Ministry of Culture, Youth & Sports, n.d.) (Offenders (Probation and Community Service) Regulations 2007) (U.S Department of State, 2013). These measures are meant to implement and comply with the provisions of Articles 37 (b) and 40 (1) of the CRC, which emphasise non-custodial alternatives to imprisonment of children in conflict with the penal provisions and promote social reintegration of children in conflict with the law.

Analysis of the Implementation of the CRC Principles

Minimum Age of Criminal Responsibility (MACR)

As reiterated above, the minimum age of criminal responsibility for children who are in conflict with the law cannot be the same as that of adults for many obvious reasons, including capacity, emotional, mental and intellectual maturity. Although the provision of Article 40 of the CRC does not set the actual ideal MACR, the international best practice dictates higher MACR thresholds of 12 years to 14 years of age. The MACR in Brunei Darussalam is 7 years, meaning that children of a very young age may acquire criminal responsibility at the age of 7. Section 82 of Brunei's Penal Code provides that nothing is an offence which is done by a child under the age of 7 years, which is an absolute immunity from criminal responsibility. However, the provision of section 83 of the Penal Code qualifies that immunity to the extent that any act done by a child above the age of 7 years and under the age of 12 years would not constitute an offence provided the child lacks mature and sufficient understanding to judge the nature and consequences of his conduct on that occasion.

The above MACR thresholds under Brunei's juvenile justice system can be considered too low by CRC standards. According to the recommendation of the UN Committee on the Rights of the Child, a minimum age of criminal responsibility below the age of 12 years is considered too low by international standards and unacceptable. According to the ICJ, the provision of section 83 of the Penal Code, which provides for criminal responsibility for children from the age of seven, is inconsistent with the State Party's obligations under Article 40(3) of the Convention. Article 40(3) of the Convention and Rule 4.1 of the United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice (the "Beijing Rules") imposed obligations on States Parties not to fix MACR at too low an age level considering the facts of emotional, mental, and intellectual maturity of the children (United Nations, 2007).

The UN CRC Committee had urged Brunei to raise the MACR significantly (Committee on the Rights of the Child, 2016). Against this backdrop, a raise of Brunei Darussalam's MARC to at least 14 years would meet the international standards and expectations of MACR in juvenile justice. A further legal reform to harmonize the Penal Code and Syariah Penal Code on the MACR in line with the recommended age of 14 years will bring about clarity and certainty in Brunei's juvenile justice system.

Best Interests of the Child (CRC Article 3)

Following Brunei Darussalam's ratification of the CRC in 1995, meaningful legal and policy reforms have been undertaken by the government within the juvenile justice system and administration. These reforms include the enactment of the Children and Young Persons Act (CYPA) and the establishment of a specialised juvenile court. The institutional commitment within the juvenile justice system to the welfare of child offenders, along with the promotion of rehabilitation and reintegration measures, is directed towards aligning with the CRC's "best interests" principles. However, there are still areas of

improvement, especially the judicial corporal punishment and low thresholds of MACR, which conflict with the best interests of the child principles.

Special Juvenile Court and Child-Friendly Justice and Procedures (CRC Articles 12 and 40)

The establishment of a special juvenile court which operates in all districts in Brunei Darussalam now promotes the ideal of the welfare of the child offenders and their rehabilitation as opposed to punitive measures. The introduction of juvenile justice has empowered magistrates who sit as presiding judicial officers in the courts to explore alternative “sentencing” options such as probation orders, community service orders, placement in an Approved School and Approved Home and placement in a Detention Centre. These orders are usually made after due consultation by magistrates with the Panel of Advisers, who deliberate extensively over the best interests of the child, and in consultation with the Probation Unit Officers.

This is a good development in the reform of the Brunei Darussalam juvenile justice system. It is also a significant alignment with the provisions of Articles 40 (3) and 40 (4) of CRC (Judiciary of Brunei Darussalam, n.d.) (CACJ ASEAN Judiciaries, n.d.) (Judiciary of Brunei Darussalam, n.d.). As reiterated above, the symbiotic institutional partnership and collaboration between the court and JAPEM, coupled with the use of care and supervision orders, have been effective in realising an integrated juvenile justice practice envisioned by the core principles of CRC. It is important to note here that the procedural rules in the CPC in respect of child or youthful offenders support child participation in the proceedings.

Diversions/Interventions and Non-Custodial Measures (Articles 37 and 40)

One of the intervention approaches provided for under Article 37 of the CRC, which State Parties are encouraged to embrace when dealing with children in conflict with the law, is a measure without resorting to judicial proceedings, especially when the alleged offence is not serious (minor offences). Another approach is the use of non-custodial sanctions. One of the areas of influence of CRC on Brunei Darussalam juvenile justice is the establishment of a probation and community service framework under the coordination of the Offenders (Probation and Community Service) regime and JAPEM’s coordinating role. The JAPEM’s role provided the basis for community-based disposition of juvenile cases.

The implementation initiative and policy development to meet CRC obligations and international minimum standards of juvenile justice are commendable. However, to strengthen CRC implementation in Brunei, the statutory requirements and checklists of diversionary measures must be codified.

Deprivation of Liberty (CRC Articles 37(b) and 40(1))

According to Article 37 (b), during juvenile justice proceedings, detention must be used only as a measure of last resort and for the shortest appropriate period. This means that a well-trained probation service is put in place by state parties for the maximum and effective use of measures such as guidance and supervision orders, probation, community monitoring or day report centers, and the possibility of early release from detention. CYPFA followed these standard measures in its provisions by authorising care, protection and supervision orders, and the specialised Juvenile Court adopted welfare orientation as an alternative to custodial measures. However, the existence of custodian sentences and low MACR in Brunei Darussalam’s juvenile justice system is not in line with the CRC and the best international standards practice.

Sentencing and Corporal Punishment

Any forms of torture, cruel and inhuman or degrading punishment are unacceptable practices in juvenile justice. Article 37(a) prohibits cruel and corporal punishment for child offenders. Available international reports indicate that judicial corporal punishment such as whipping remains part of Brunei’s juvenile justice practices. Within the Syariah framework, punishments in the form of whipping will apply to children or adolescents in certain circumstances (International Commission of Jurists, 2015) (Child Rights International Network, 2012) (Child Rights International Network, 2010).

It is instructive to note that Brunei Darussalam is under obligation under CRC to prohibit any forms of cruel, torture, or corporal punishment in relation to juvenile justice and not to impose on persons for offences committed under 18 years, whether tried under the Penal Code, Syariah Penal Code, or any other forum or legal regime of juvenile justice in Brunei Darussalam. It is therefore suggested that there is the need to generally legislate on the prohibition of judicial corporal punishment for persons under 18 years of age across civil and Syariah court jurisdictions in Brunei Darussalam. Such proposed legislation should emphasise that children are exempted from any form of torture or cruel, inhuman, or degrading punishment, including corporal punishment. If this is done, it will bring Brunei Darussalam's juvenile justice system in compliance with the provision of Article 37(a) of the CRC.

Guarantees for a Fair Trial and Adequate Legal Assistance

The list of important rights and guarantees for a fair trial, including legal assistance for adequate representation in juvenile justice proceedings, to ensure that every child alleged as an accused of having infringed the penal law is provided for under Article 40 (2) of the CRC. The Article of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) also provided for similar rights as the minimum guarantees for a fair trial under Article 40(2) of the CRC. These rights, among others, include the right to receive prompt information on charges, the right to have the case determined without undue delay and the case to be determined by an independent and impartial authority, and the right to appeal.

Although the Criminal Procedure Code (Cap. 7, revised 2016) applies to Brunei Darussalam Juvenile Justice procedure under CYPA and court practice (Child and Young Persons Act 2010) (Criminal Procedure Code 1951) (Penal Code 1951). Brunei's procedural rules, as they are applicable to juvenile justice, are expected to guarantee a fair trial in juvenile justice proceedings. However, unhindered access to justice and legal representation stands as cardinal factors to evaluate a fair trial. Generally, Brunei has a limited legal aid system, and it lacks a formal legal aid system for juvenile justice as well. State-funded legal aid is reserved for defendants facing the death penalty. Legal representations are usually through private lawyers, and as reiterated above, with state legal aid reserved for capital cases. The Brunei Law Society president underscores the imperative of a fair trial and legal representation, saying, "Everyone has the right to a fair hearing and representation" (The Scoop, 2018). In the interest of improving access to justice and legal representation, the Law Society launched a legal aid fund to assist Bruneians who cannot afford legal representation in criminal cases, including juvenile justice proceedings.

Institutional Coordination in Child Protection

Brunei Darussalam's juvenile justice system is a multi-sectoral and inter-agency collaboration designed to meet the needs of the Child and Young Persons (CYP) and protect their rights in accordance with the core principles of CRC. The collaboration between the specialized juvenile court that operated in the four districts and the JAPEM under CYPA represents an integrated approach towards the realization of efficient and effective protection of child rights. JAPEM, being designated as the lead agency for multi-sectoral child protection coordination, has been active in the management and risk assessment of juvenile cases. Other agencies and institutions involved in child protection activities and who are also represented in the Brunei Child Protection Committee (CPC) are the Attorney General's Office, the Royal Brunei Police Force, the Ministry of Health, the Ministry of Education, the Narcotics Control Bureau, the Ministry of Home Affairs and the Ministry of Religious Affairs.

The CPC serves as a forum for inter-agency collaboration and a platform for discussions and collective decision-making on child protection cases. The Action Team on Child Protection, chaired by the Permanent Secretary of the Ministry of Culture, Youth and Sports, is responsible for policy formulation and strategic considerations on juvenile justice matters and most especially the enhancement of the protection of child rights in Brunei Darussalam. Despite this stride, there is a need for formal standard operating procedures between agencies that are involved in child rights protection to improve inter-agency collaboration.

Recommendations

It is evident from the foregoing discussion that Brunei Darussalam has made tremendous improvement in her juvenile justice system following the ratification of the CRC in December 1995 despite the reservations on Articles 4, 20, and 21 on the ground that they are in conflict with the Constitution and Syariah principles. However, there are some important areas of the juvenile justice system and administration that call for policy, legal, and structural reforms. These include the following.

Legal Reform

There is a call for raising the MACR in Brunei Darussalam to at least 14, and preferably 15-16 years across all criminal jurisdictions in Brunei Darussalam. The present provision of sections 82 and 83 of the Penal Code sets a narrow and low MACR. It is therefore recommended that sections 82 and 83 of the Penal Code be repealed or amended in reflection of the global best practice and CRC guidance. Brunei Darussalam may need to consider a total prohibition of corporal punishment as it relates to child offenders. There are other alternatives and correctional measures to achieve rehabilitation and reintegration of child offenders into society. As part of the legal reforms necessary is the harmonisation of all statutes and policies on juvenile justice in Brunei Darussalam. Here the provisions of the Syariah Penal Code, the Penal Code, CPC, and CYPAs all have to be aligned in accordance with the CRC core principles, especially about MACR and protective evidentiary rules.

Policy and Practice Reform to Strengthen Diversion Programmes and Restorative Justice

To achieve efficient and effective protection of child rights, Brunei Darussalam needs to explore diversion from judicial proceedings in juvenile justice and the use of non-custodial sanctions. Although diversion and non-custodial measures are part of Brunei Darussalam's juvenile justice system, for effective use of diversion, diversion guidelines need to be codified for the use of police and prosecutors. The diversion guidelines should spell out measures such as police cautions, family conferences, restorative victim-offender mediations, and referrals. Brunei Darussalam's probation and community service framework under the Offenders (Probation and Community Service) regime and JAPEM's coordinating role, which provide a basis for community-based dispositions and measures, need to be expanded.

Governance and Promotion of Independent Monitoring

Brunei Darussalam's efforts to achieve a child-centred juvenile justice system in alignment with international child rights standards hinge on establishing good governance and independent monitoring of the juvenile justice system and administration. Effective juvenile justice governance will require periodic publication of juvenile justice statistics, diversion, detention, custodial sentences, and prompt submission of CRC and Optional Protocol reports to maintain credibility and demonstrate commitment to international standards.

Review of Reservations to Articles 14, 20, and 21 of the CRC

Brunei Darussalam, when ratifying the CRC in 1995, entered general and specific reservations in respect of Articles 14 (freedom of thoughts, conscience, and religion), 20 (protection of children deprived of their family environment), and 21 (adoption). The reservations are predicated upon Brunei's preservation of her Islamic principles and customary law that uniquely shaped the family system and child protection policies. A gradual review of these reservations may be considered by the Brunei Darussalam government to enhance the regime of child rights and compliance with international standards if it will not fundamentally whittle down the Islamic principles and customs on family systems and child protection (Schabas, 1996).

Conclusion

Brunei Darussalam's juvenile justice system and administration have evolved over the years following the ratification of the CRC in 1995. Its transformational stages reflect the quest to institutionalize a juvenile justice system that is child rights centered and in substantial compatibility with CRC core principles and

other international human rights best standards for the protection of children who are in conflict with the penal law. Brunei Darussalam has taken giant steps in this direction, and notable among them are the establishment of special juvenile courts operating in all four districts, the enactment of juvenile legislation, and community-based structures through JAPEM, among other legal, policy and structural initiatives.

Despite the above development, there are salient challenges that are yet to be addressed in relation to child rights protection in Brunei Darussalam. Among them are the low thresholds of MACR, the use of corporal punishment in juvenile justice, the dual child rights tracks, and the consistency of protection under civil/criminal and Syariah systems. It is hoped that Brunei Darussalam's next effort at reforming the juvenile justice system will address these concerns.

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